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Evaluation & Impact Assessment
INTEREST-INFLUENCE MATRIX

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>To be used iteratively throughout the project/initiative to assess and improve network membership and collaborative relationships.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Small to large multi actor group.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>Basic Microsoft Word skills required if that option is selected.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>1-2 hrs each time the evaluation is done (depending on group size & extent of discussion needed internally or/and with stakeholders). The interpretation may take another 1-2 hrs or more.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Requires basic materials. Can be conducted physically with internal/external participants in a room or online. The online option implies filling the Microsoft Word Tool (see template). At least one facilitator is required.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 1, 3.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

The analysis can be made at one point of time only, or at 2 or 3 consecutive periods of time. We recommend the latter as it allows us to see the evolution of the network of actors over time.

The Tool can be used multiple times, e.g. at the periods 'A', 'B' and 'C'. This evaluation can be done in quasi real time, but also in an ex-post manner. An ex-post assessment means that the evaluator will reconstruct the network as it was at the period of interest.

The above figure represents the Interest-Influence matrix and indicates the four categories resulting from the crossroad between the level of Influence/Power of stakeholders as well as the level of Interest of stakeholders.

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Identify crucial actors that shape the network and/or boost the innovation according to their influence/power and interest
- Identify actors that negatively affect the actors and/or undermine the innovation according to their influence/power and interest
- Monitor the role of actors according to their influence/power and interest and adapt the strategy/activities accordingly.

The best case scenario is when both the Interest and Influence/Power of the stakeholders is high. The implications of the other scenarios depends on the context but, in principle, the higher the interest, the better.

In terms of data source, two options are possible:

- The evaluator makes its own estimation;
- The evaluator involves key actors to estimate the level of Influence and Interest/Power of stakeholders.

Background and Logic

The Interest-Influence Microsoft Word Tool aims to support practitioners in evaluating project-based interactive innovations.

The objective of making an Interest-Influence matrix is to identify the stakeholders that are important for the interactive innovation project, in the sense that they significantly influence it. It is a priori important to also consider stakeholders that influence much the interactive innovation, but that are not necessarily very interactive with the others.

The choice between the two above options should be based on three criteria: (1) time investment, (2) financial and human resources, and (3) the degree of knowledge of the auditor and other actors on the level of Influence and Interest/Power of stakeholders.

Materials

- Flipchart paper
- Sticky notes
- Thick dark markers.

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1

- In case a workshop is conducted, explain the purpose, logic and background of the exercise.
- Ask participants to write their **name and an 'actor identifier'** on a sticky note (either physically in an in-person meeting or virtually).
- Actor identifiers depend on the orientation of the multi-actor project. For example, in a Horizon 2020 Thematic Network, the actor identifiers may include research, education, SME and extension. The diversity of actors (and their actor identifiers) are typically cited in funding applications, as a credential of the project's multi-actor approach. The group can be reminded of the importance of including different actor categories, and asked to reflect on the actor category they are representing in the group/network/project.
- It is important to explain to the group that some actors may have other/several actor identifiers. Ask them to reflect on the particular role/s they will/have in the project in choosing their actor identifiers. They may choose more than one identifier, but it is important for actors to represent the actor category/ies they are representing in the project/ assigned in a grant agreement, where relevant.

Step 2

Depending on whether the evaluator wished to involve stakeholders or not, the exercise may be participatory or not. Should it be participatory (recommended), all stakeholders should reflect on the position of the different actors within the matrix and a collective agreement is to be found.

The actors' name should be written/specified on separate sticky notes and placed within the matrix, depending on their level of Interest and Influence/Power. In the appendix is an example where actors ('At1, At2, etc.) are placed within the matrix.

The Tool attached to this guide is available in a Word A4 but also A3 format, depending on the needs; the evaluator can create text areas (click on Insert, create text area) in which the actor's full name or acronym is specified. Another possibility is simply to print the empty matrix, and fill it manually. Finally, the matrix can be drawn on a poster, which would be particularly appropriate in a workshop setting.

Appendix

